

Mixed Use of Different Atmospheric Cues to Create Unique Store Architect and its Effect on Buying Behavior

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Abstract: Retailing has been changing facet in the country. The retail industry is one of the most established industries in the world. In the Asian-Pacific nations, consistent rise in the proportion of the best 250 retailers was observed. In developing countries growth has been consistent, instigated by state reforms that have motivated investing. The demographic setting has also played a key role in boosting growth in the retail industry. This paper adopts four store atmospheric cues namely store layout, music, light, and cleanliness as they have been noted to have more significant cues and make positive impact on customer buying behaviour. Questionnaire method used to collect the data from apparel store and further analysed by SPSS 22 and AMOS 22 statistical software and generated SEM model to checked hypothesis. Results show that selected store cues make positive impact on customer emotions and persuade them to visit in future for shopping.

Keywords: Atmospherics, Store Exterior, Store Interior, Color, Lighting, Music, Scent, Store Image and Retail Positioning

1. Introduction

The present day competitive setting for retailers initiates the need to obtain in-depth information regarding the store atmosphere that specifically touches on the customer's selection of the store, purchase intent, and loyalty so as to advance the purchaser's attitude regarding the store to influence their behavior (Shamsher, 2016). Several studies have confirmed the influence of the environment on customer behavior, thus leading to the

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observation that the store atmosphere influences the customers view and attitude (Donovan and Rossiter, 1982; Xu and Chen, 2017; Hussain and Ali, 2015) which further sways the service and quality of the store atmosphere (Lindberga et al., 2018).

Traditional retailers in physical outlets need to leverage their ability of creating an alluring physical setting in order to achieve competitive advantage. This will enhance their control in inviting and gratifying clients as the milieu in retail premises is the main competitive approach applied by merchants to excite customer experience and raise products sales (Hanaysha, 2018). Focus on retail atmosphere will place the brick-and-mortar retailers in a better position to offer unmatched services compared to retailers who sell their products only on the online platform (Zentes et al., 2018). In 2017, outstanding expansion of the retail industry in the Middle East was observed because of the concentration in establishing brick and mortar stores. The most noticed growth in these stores was in Asia-Pacific where growth rate amounted to over 1% which, according to Stevens (2018), was stimulated by the gratifying experiences in physical outlets. What is interesting to note, however, is the fact that most customers first accessed information about different products online as the first step in their purchase process. This is important in that it presents an avenue through which brick and mortar stores can use technology in increasing sales in their physical stores.

At present, low sales performance has threatened major retailers resulting from the dynamic purchasing attitude and thus prompting interest to understand customer behaviour (Zentes et al., 2018). Research by Sigurdsson et al., (2016) shows that majority of retailer neglect to look into the behaviour of customers within the store and opt to increase income through other means. These other means include discussing discounts or requesting for other marketing grants with manufacturers, adding charges, or sometimes bargaining with the premises management instead of following through income obtained from selling. This leads to the third research question, 'Can the brick and mortar retailers increase sales by taking advantage of the store atmosphere to positively influence customers and increase profitability?'

2. Literature Review

2.1. Visual merchandising and store atmospheric cues

Various store atmospheric cues elements have been used analyse the influence of store atmosphere on the direct impact on customer behaviour or through the emotional impact of pleasure and arousal. The study focuses on the organized apparel segment where the living model has changed and the sector has been expanding at a high rate despite the challenges of extreme competition caused by increased number of retailers (Shukla, Vyas and Pandya, 2018). In-store fashion sales people implement the use of visual

merchandising to influence purchasing through prompting customers of their wants and desires, and could create a wanted store atmosphere that heightens customer purchasing pleasure and arousal (Balgaoonkar, Pabalkar and Yelikar, 2014). In the apparel segment, customers are persistently presented with new-fangled products assortments by the different stores to continuously develop awareness and provoke purchasing (Shukla, Vyas and Pandya, 2018).

Figure 1: Mehrabian and Russell model

Source: Nell (2013).

Pleasure is defined as the consequential feeling customers experience in response to the way they have found the new surrounding in relation to being amusing and gratifying or not pleasing, arousal describes the intensity of the environment stimuli on the customers and dominance concentrates on the power the customer perceives in the environment (Nell, 2013) to the buyer for use and not further selling. CARE Ratings (2017) described retailing as the purchasing of different goods in huge measures from diverse points of buying such as manufacturers to be later sold in small measures directly to the consumer. According to Pattanaik and Mishra (2016), all firms that sell products or services from manufacturers, wholesalers, agents, importers, or other retailers to consumers for their own use by having a store or any other means using diverse selling models such as by mail, telephone, vending machine, in person or via the world wide web are undertaking the business of retailing.

Visual merchandising is defined as a process that concentrates on stimulating the prospective customer into purchasing products and is implemented through the external or internal sections of the stores where it has been found to have great influence in promoting sales of a store (Balgaoonkar, Pabalkar and Yelikar, 2014). Visual merchandising elements consist of external displays, store layout, internal displays, atmospherics, light, music scent, colour, and location descriptors with the intention of initiating impulse buying (Mihic et al., 2018). The store marketers are embracing innovative store models including layout structure by using visual stimulators of marketing on the good-looking packaging, striking displays, and suitable locations for promoted products in the store instigating visual merchandising to be a critical strategic marketing action in rising the number of visitors and sales in the stores (Shukla, Vyas and Pandya, 2018).

Visual merchandising entails the arrangement of the store and other components that build the total outlook of the store and is important as more than eighty percent of excites are generated from observation and every customer has their own conceptualised picture of the store and its products (Balgaonkar, Pabalkar and Yelikar, 2014). A study conducted by Mihić et al (2018) showed that visual merchandising is the most key influencer of spending time in fashion stores hence proposing that visual merchandising offers a positive store atmosphere leading to approach behaviour which could be further transferred to purchasing.

Shukla, Vyas and Pandya (2018) analysed four extents of visual merchandising which included window display, internal display, floor retailing and advertisement signage to gauge their impact on increased number of visitors stores located in the Vadodara city of the Gujarat State in India but this study will adopt four store atmospheric cues namely *store layout, music, light, and cleanliness* as they have been noted to have more significance in influencing both the visual and olfactory senses of customers and are the most important elements to consider when wanting to positively impact on the customer behavior with anticipation of more sales since they do not need substantial funds to implement and the store features are readily available to be implemented by store sales people in the apparel section.

2.2. Store layout

Store layout is categorized into two ways, the first is the grid layout which is created by arranging aisles in a systematic order with the aim of providing easy accessibility to products hence being quick and effective, and the second is the free-form layout that is developed by organizing the store without any order, the aisles, exhibition stands and racks are neatly but set without restrictions with the intention of inciting curiosity and can be configure in different ways (Jang, Baek, Yoon and Choo, 2018).

Within the store, displays include product displays, purchasing point, shelf space, signs, and wall beautifications which are known to be critical in the retail store marketing tactic as product displays heighten the customer's mindfulness to advertisements, promotional campaigns, and prices, and reduces the faithfulness to brand increasing the chances of impulse buying though not for premediated buying (Bohl, 2012). Window displays are usually placed at the front of the store to attract the attention of customers to the stores and show the products existing in the store and thus an elegant window display store frontage is an important way of inciting new clientele to enter the store (Nishanov and Ahunjonov, 2016).

The store layout and display of products in a store prompts the customer's interest to move around and scrutinize the products thereby initiating purchasing as the manner in which a

product is positioned in a store and how it is remarked upon, impacts on the customer's view of the product, buying plan, and customer's decision in purchasing (Hussain and Ali, 2015; Van Vliet, 2018). The beautification of the store, suitability, coziness, and space increase responsiveness of probable customers and provides room for socializing (Xu and Chen, 2017).

To maximize on the store layout, the arrangement of products should be in a way that the most number of products are displayed and the store arrangement should be configured to provide sufficient space between the aisles and ensure paths are not overcrowded by products (Mathur and Goswami, 2014). Research has shown that a quarter of the sales in retail stores is as a result of the exhibition of products, thus products in retail stores should be placed in a manner that customers are stimulated and attracted to influence unplanned purchasing (Hussain and Ali, 2015). In the apparel segment, stores are encouraged to maximize on the clothing display and make visible the material features, among others with the aim of increasing the products viewed value and plus being compliant with new upcoming designs (Xu and Chen, 2017). Crowded stores have been known to reduce the level of satisfaction, view of quality and thus affect the product sales (Van Vliet, 2018).

Mohan et al (2013) noted that a properly organized store layout reduces the time for searching for products and thus provides convenience to customers through ease in identifying products. Store layout and display have been scrutinized by many researchers and found to have influence on consumer behavior (Zou and Wakiyama, 2018; Munshi, 2018; Hussain and Ali, 2018). Mehta (2014) proposed significant influence of window display to unplanned purchasing. Other studies have indicated that products are highly selected if they are placed in a wide shelf space though widening the shelf space does not guarantee more sales, shelves have been noted to be best placed when they are below the eye level in many product categories (Bohl, 2012).

Mower, Kim and Childs (2012) examined the exterior atmospheric structure with emphasis on window displays on customers' reactions to an apparel boutique in relation to feeling good at the store, the ambiance, and fondness using data compiled from students at an American university and applying the theoretic model suggested by Mehrabian and Russell of the stimulus organism response (SOR) model. The data was analyzed using univariate and simple regression analyses where the results showed that window display was not significant to influence pleasure or arousal although the existence of window display impacted on the customer's feeling good about the store and thus being fond of the store. The study advocated for store retailers, particularly apparel stores to put more concentration on their window displays.

Few studies have checked the effect of store layout in terms of having enough space to walk around easily, the floor space arrangement and ease in finding other products in the

apparel category sought, the display of product information using window display, and the importance of display and layout in apparel purchasing on the influence of the emotions in customers and their behaviour. Therefore, to critically investigate the influence of store layout and display on customer behavior, the following secondary hypothesis was set.

H1: Store layout and display have a significant influence on pleasure, arousal, customer experiences and customer behavior intention.

The secondary hypothesis was divided into specific impacted areas to provide more insight on the specific influence of each store atmospheric cue on customer behavior using the direct relationship and indirect relationships of using the emotional impact. The following primary hypothesis was set:

H1_a: Store layout and display on pleasure

H1_b: Store layout and display on arousal

H1_c: Store layout and display on customer experiences

H1_d: Store layout and display on customer behaviour intention

2.3. Music

The practice of using music in retail setting has been researched in psychology and in influencing people's behavior and retailers adopts the use of music as a stimulus in the buying resolution of customers in diverse business settings since music is easy to implement and manage and also it is not invasive to customers (Santos and Freire, 2013).

Music is an agreeable sound that controls customer's judgements consciously or subconsciously (Banat and Wandebori, 2012) and in the retail stores, music is used to influence customer buying intention (Hussain and Ali, 2015). Suitable background music in stores provides customers with a looked-for store atmosphere that describes the store image and determines the customer's selection of store and it has been shown that incorporating the correct type of music, there is an unswervingly positive effect on customer behaviour in the store (Farias et al, 2014).

The kind of background music played in the store substantially influences the customer opinions and fondness (Hussain and Ali, 2015). When favoured music is aired at a store, customers who desire such type of music become calm, contented, easy, happy and experience increased pleasure while purchasing thus spending more time and consequently there is high possibility of buying additional items than planned including inducing the approach behaviour due to the emotional feeling of gratification and required customer experience whereas when the store atmosphere is noisy, wild, and loud, it may cause uneasiness and customers will opt to utilize as little time as possible at the store and may avoid the store in future (Ali et al, 2017). Gender has been noted to moderate the influence

of high volume on music liking as females have responded unfavourably compared to males on loud music (Hussain and Ali, 2015).

Nishanov and Ahunjonov (2016) noted that music is a critical feature of the store atmosphere to stimulate customer purchasing behaviour where music was found to encourage unplanned behaviour instigated by the customers consuming more time that results from the playing of desired background music which initiates continued looking around the store and noticing different products that motivate purchasing. Hussain and Ali (2015) stated that music has a fruitful influence on the customers' amount of time and money expended in the store as a result of worthy environment. Several studies have analysed the influence of music on the emotional view of pleasure and arousal, on customer experience and on customer behaviour.

Vaccaro, et al. (2011) analysed the influence of desired atmospheric music on customer attitude based on three emotional states that were happiness, sadness, and irritating, previous purchasing experience, and comeback intents in retail and service environments by distributing a survey questionnaire to 248 respondents who had visited the targeted retail and services stores. Questions revolved around desired ambience, music extents, avoidance and returning activities and previous store experience. The findings indicated that desired music is associated to previous purchasing experience and also to the emotional state of happiness where customers had their most purchasing intents.

With the various evidence of influence of music in enhancing emotions, customer experience and customer behaviour, this study analysed music in terms of how the music in the store matches the customer's mood, how the store music makes their shopping more entertaining, how the store music feels while continuing with purchasing in relation to boredom, how the store music excites the customer to search for more products, how the store music changes the customer's purchasing emotions, how the high and low volume background music in the store changes the customer's emotions and whether the store should be adjusting the volume of music with time. The following hypothesis was set to analyse these effects on the customer behaviour.

H2: Store music has a significant influence on pleasure, arousal, customer experiences and customer behavior intention.

To evaluate the impact of music on a more insightful approach, the secondary hypothesis was divided into specific impacted areas similar to H1 and the following primary hypotheses were set.

H2_a: Store music on pleasure

H2_b: Store music on arousal

H2_c: Store music on customer experiences

H2_d: Store music on customer behaviour intention

2.4. Light

Light is mainly incorporated in stores to highlight products and create easiness for the customers to consider observing the product keenly and encourage the customers to touch and feel the products aiming at checking the eminence and features thereby positively stimulating buying behavior through the interest and eagerness to explore the product (Hussain and Ali, 2015). As indicated by Ali et al (2017), Light influences the customer behavior but the customers are ignorant of the diverse types of lighting, for example, lighting increases the rate of processing transactions in the store and thus enhancing convenience to both the customers and retailers although stores should avoid too much light to prevent excess brightness. According to Hussain and Ali (2015), the lighting of a store has an impact on the store selection by customers and encourages loyalty to the store. Borges, Babin and Spielmann (2013) articulated that the blending of the lighting has a significant bearing in the store's ability to attract purchasing and loyalty.

The general intensity and shade of the lighting in the store has been illustrated to have an effect on buying intents and products sales (Spence et al, 2014). Elena and Jakub (2014) highlighted that the different kinds of lighting have an effect on the functioning of the brain, expressing that light has a substantial effect on the knowingly and unknowingly customer responses where light has thus been seen as a primary marketing instrument to motivate customers and rise selling of the products. To increase efficiency, lighting should be standardized within the store and dim to ensure customers are comfortable with the store (Ali et al, 2017).

Stores implement the use of lighting to prompt and attain the ideal level of motivation that will inspire positive customer behavior, for instance, the administrators of store usually probe to ascertain the satisfactory brightness required to have the optimum level of customer motivate on either by reducing or increasing the intensity of light (Spence et al, 2014). Sufficient lighting has been seen to portray a sign of cleanliness and superior products quality and therefore apparel stores should have utilized the advantage of lighting to highlight the fineness of the products (Nell, 2013). Ali et al (2017) expressed that lighting is among the store atmospheric cues that aid in initiating a feeling of enjoyment in the store where clear lighting tempts shoppers to react in a positive manner by giving a pure color view of the products in the store in addition to making the products more attractive and lighting provides customers with an extensive view of the products in the store.

Mixed results have been observed in studies relating to the effect of lighting on pleasure and arousal, customer experience and customer behavior, though an effect on customer behavior is inevitable. Quartier, Vanrie and Van Cleempoel (2014) undertook a study to investigate the actual impact of lighting on observed atmosphere and resultant behavior in

three retail stores in Belgium by using two models of environment which were completely modified to represent the retail stores and a mirror and cameras installed to check the in-store perusing behavior on path taken, pace of walking, and time used in the store using a sample of 95 persons, some were students while other were the general populace where 30 were men and 65 were women whom were in the age range from 18 to 63 and the respondents were not notified of the aim of study. In the models, only lighting settings were altered and the level of motivation in emotions and behavior were gauged on view of the atmosphere on three scopes of disinterestedness namely, relaxation in terms of pleasing, agreeable, and friendly among others, vivacity in terms of joyful, exciting arousing, and Uneasiness in terms of domineering, stressed, and worrisome. Next, store image was examined and lastly the emotions were also scrutinized. The study found the environment set with warm lighting and accent lighting on the product groups initiated more enjoyment in respondent's feelings which was also linked to the relaxation and vivacity, and a decline in uneasiness.

Light has been observed to have an effect on emotions, customer experience and customer behaviour and this study has analysed lighting in terms of how the store light is attractive, how the brightening of the store influences attention, how the lighting assists to find products easily and see clearly, how dull light caused attraction to certain products, how the store light affects the stimulation and feeling of happiness, and lastly how the apparel store should implement the most appropriate combination of lighting. The following hypothesis was set to analyse these effects on the customer behaviour.

H3: Store light has a significant influence on pleasure, arousal, customer experiences and customer behavior intention.

To evaluate the impact of light on a more insightful approach, the secondary hypothesis was divided into specific impacted areas similar to H1 and the following primary hypothesis were set.

H3_a: Store light on pleasure

H3_b: Store light on arousal

H3_c: Store light on customer experiences

H3_d: Store light on customer behaviour intention

2.5. Cleanliness

The store cleanliness reflects on its look and aids in improving the store's atmosphere which has an effect on the customers feel in regards to the store as cleanliness provides a positive opinion of the store and encourage customers to spend more time in the store and thus may prompt additional buying through providing the customers with a view of cosiness and extravagance (Hussain and Ali, 2015). Older people have been noted to be

uncomfortable with unwanted odours and lack of cleanliness in addition to being tricked by sales people through intense marketing (Bohl, 2012).

Banat and Wandebori (2012) note that customers spread positive or negative rumours about a store by observing the cleanliness. The look and behaviour of sellers in a store influences the customer's view of the store and thus in turn has an effect on the customer's behaviour towards the store, for instance, sellers who wear dishonourable clothing have been seen to inhibit customer's provenance of the store and reduce the level of happiness and contentment (Bohl, 2012).

Welcoming and approachable sales people are plainly noticeable and easy to identify hence their presence in satisfactory numbers enhances the customer's experience by anticipating improved service hence influences the customer behaviour and buying intention (Vliet, 2018). Bohl (2012) noted that stores with sales people that are interactive with customers such as saluting them, customers viewed the stores to have better customer experience than those where the sales people did not salute the customers and thus the sociability of sales people has a positive sway on the emotional aspects of pleasure and arousal which could be transferred to purchasing intention. Enough lighting has been known to indicate a sign of cleanliness as the products and general layout of the store is clearly seen (Nell, 2013).

Many studies have analysed the effect of cleanliness on stimulating customers and driving pleasure and arousal, customer experience and changing customer behaviour. Widiyani (2018) analysed cleanliness in shopping malls and found it to have significant influence on customer behaviour in all types of retail shops. Thahir and Krishnapillai (2017) analysed the store atmospherics of cafes in Ipoh, Perak using a questionnaire directed to 250 respondents and applied partial least squares model to evaluate the data received and among the store atmospheric cues, cleanliness was found to influence revisiting intention hence play a role in impacting on the customer's experience and behaviour through satisfaction and loyalty.

Cleanliness has an influence on emotions, customer experience and customer behaviour and this study has analysed cleanliness in terms of the store being clean and tidy to improve customer's wellbeing and comfort, to examine dirt and purchasing intentions, to check whether the store hygiene increases customer's trust factor about the store products, to check whether the dressing of sales people affect the customer's experience, to analysed whether the sociability of sales people causes irritation to customers, to confirm whether professional service which includes guidance from sales people makes the customer feel valued, to confirm whether the experience encountered prompts future buying, and to confirm whether apparel stores require professional service and hygiene. The following hypothesis was set to analyse these effects on the customer behaviour.

H4: Store cleanliness has a significant influence on pleasure, arousal, customer experiences and customer behavior intention.

To evaluate the impact of cleanliness on a more insightful approach, the secondary hypothesis was divided into specific impacted areas similar to H1 and the following primary hypotheses were set.

H4_a: Store cleanliness on pleasure

H4_b: Store cleanliness on arousal

H4_c: Store cleanliness on customer experiences

H4_d: Store cleanliness on customer behaviour intention

2.6. Pleasure, arousal, and customer experience on consumer behaviour

The in-store retailers mainly focus on the hedonic approach since customer choice is encouraged by emotional elements and not sensible motive, causing the vendors to spend on experimental marketing stratagems and devote to establishing an exceptional in-store feeling aiming at upgrading customer faithfulness and increasing products sales, subsequently, elevating the amusement on customers when purchasing products and thus winning over customers to make purchases through emotional attachment as opposed to purchases made on the practicality of the advantages (Venter et al, 2018) as in the case of online shopping.

As noted by Lindberga et al (2018), understanding the multisensory retail situation in influencing customer's view and attitude towards purchasing is a key approach to motivate buying and includes the five senses that are vision, hearing, olfaction, touch, and taste. With the advancement in focusing on customer experience, the sensory marketing model to improve the customer experience where the store atmospherics are progressively being intended to invite customers both sensible and emotional points including through the multiple senses and the broad way of creating additional connecting sensory points with customers is an innovative approach to introduce uniqueness in the market arena (Spence et al, 2014). In marketing studies, the sensory approach concentrates on vision, audition, or olfaction (Spence et al, 2014). Bohl (2012) noted that atmospheric cues offer stimulation that heightens the possibility creating an enjoyable environment which then makes the customers to spend more time in this environment to increase the level of contentment from the environment and in retail setting, it prompts continued purchasing. Sabrina (2014) noted that pleasure and arousal in the store is created by various store atmospherics that have a positive influence on customer purchasing. Perera and Sutha (2018) expressed that shopping has evolved from a need basis to an enjoyment venture where people randomly visit shops to pass time and not visiting with the intention of purchasing.

Ridgway, Dawson and Bloch (1989) undertook a study to analyze individual reactions to environments in an outdoor retail market using a questionnaire that focused on pleasure and arousal on patronage behaviors. The study discovered that customer's emotional reaction to an environment is critical in influencing patronage behaviors and outlooks. Azam and Gupta, (2018) analysed the impact of several stores atmospheric features on consumer's inclination in the choice of apparel retail outlets through collecting data from 180 buyers and grouping the features into six elements that influence apparel retail namely recreation, rendition, rapport, rate, range and recurrence. The study found that pleasurable and arousal while purchasing was the most favoured choice against product superiority, price, and discount offered for the current buyers to choose the retail outlet.

The influence of pleasure, arousal and customer experience on customer behaviour is undoubted and this study analysed the effect of these elements separately. Pleasure was analysed by checking whether the customer felt satisfied, happy, lazy, pleased, increased fun, or hopeless within the stores and the following hypothesis was set to analyse these effects on the customer behaviour.

H5: Store pleasure has a significant influence on customer experiences and customer behavior intention.

To evaluate the impact of pleasure on a more insightful approach, the secondary hypothesis was divided into specific impacted areas similar to H1 and the following primary hypotheses were set.

H5_a: Store pleasure on customer experience

H5_b: Store pleasure on customer behaviour

In the study, arousal was analysed in terms of the customer feeling excited, more energetic, sleepy, stimulated, relaxed, and comfortable in this store generating the following hypothesis.

H6: Store arousal has a significant influence on customer experiences and customer behavior intention.

To evaluate the impact of arousal on a more insightful approach, the secondary hypothesis was divided into specific impacted areas similar to H1 and the following primary hypothesis were set.

H6_a: Store arousal on customer experience

H6_b: Store arousal on customer behaviour

Lastly, the study analysed the effect of customer experience on customer behaviour by checking whether the customer felt good while shopping, felt good while interaction with

sales people in the store, and checked whether the current experience was preferred to prior experience. The following hypothesis was set.

H7: Store customer experience has a significant influence on customer behavior intention.

The following primary hypotheses were set.

H7_a: Store customer experience on customer behaviour

This research is designed to gauge the influence of store atmosphere cues on consumer behavior in the organized apparel retail, to identify the elements of store atmosphere cues and mediating factors that influence consumer behavior in the organized apparel retail.

3. Research Framework

To enhance understanding of the research, a research process based on the Mehrabian and Russell (1974) view and the theory of planned behavior as stipulated by Xiao et al (2014) in customer behavior intention was adopted. Influencing the emotional aspect of the customer during shopping has become an important strategy to many companies. At present, the customer store experience which mainly looks at the customer's happiness is realized by modifying the store purposely to encourage positive customer behavior response towards the store and its products.

The study was driven by the desire to identify the store atmospheric cues that would enhance the shopping experience of the customers to either match or be above their expectations and also positively influence their emotional state during the shopping period. To achieve this, the paper concentrated on the elements that influence the overall Customer Behavior Intention through direct means of the store atmospheric cues selected or through the indirect means of impacting on the Customer Retail Experience and emotional states of Pleasure and Arousal.

Using review of historical literature, the study identified the visual merchandising store elements to have more impact on the Apparel segment and adopted four key in-store atmospheric cue elements that could probably inspire positive Customer Behavior Intention, Customer Retail Experience and customer emotional state. The four store atmospheric cues chosen included Store Layout and Display, Music, Lighting, and Cleanliness and Participant

The hypotheses and the model employed for measurement were formulated for the independent and dependent variables to explain the relationships between Layout and display, lighting, music, cleanliness and participant factors on Customer Retail Experiences including Arousal, Pleasure, and Customer Behavior Intention as shown in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Research model framework

4. Methodology

This research has based on is a qualitative, exploratory research which includes two separate groups of samples. First one being Clothing stores visited customer and their store manager’s based on literature studied and researcher’s previous experience in the apparel industry, simple random sampling was used in selecting the representative clothes retailers under study.

5. Finding and Data Analysis

Figure 3: Generated S-E-M Model and its Observed Outcome

6. Variances of Dependent and Independent Variables

The predicting capability of a model can be accessed by the sum of variance detailed by independent variables in the dependent variables. The superior the amount of variance higher shall be model predicting potential. In structural equation modeling analysis, the value of variance is reported in terms of squared multiple correlations associated to dependent variables. It is equivalent to R value in Regression Analysis. The squared multiple correlations of dependent variables of the study are shown in table given below.

As can be seen from table 1, the four store atmospheric factors, i.e., store display and layout, store music, store light and store cleanliness and participant act as independent variables for pleasure, arousal, customer retail experiences and behaviour intention. The four store atmospherics elements explained as 68.4% of variation in pleasure and 57.4% of variance in arousal, 71.7% of variance in customer retail experience and 73.4% of variance

in Behaviour Intention. This means that these entire store atmospherics factor is good enough to predict and well explained emotional behaviour than cognition. For the customer retail experience, the independent variables are Store Display and Light, Music, Light and Cleanliness and participant. These independent variables explained by 71.7% of variance in customer retail experience.

Table 1 Variance by Structural Model

S. No.	Dependent Variable	Independent Variable	Squared Multiple Correlation (R)
1	Pleasure	Store Display and Layout, Music, Light and Cleanliness and Participant.	0.684
2	Arousal	Store Display and Layout, Music, Light and Cleanliness and Participant.	0.714
3	Customers Retail Experience	Store Display and Layout, Music, Light and Cleanliness and Participant.	0.575
4	Behaviour Intention	Store Display and Layout, Music, Light and Cleanliness and Participant.	0.734

Sources: Primary Data Analysis with use of SPSS-22, AMOS-22.

For the Behaviour Intention, the independent variables are Store Display and Light, Music, Light and Cleanliness and participant. These independent variables explained by 73.4% of variance in Behaviour Intention. This indicates that customer retail experience and behaviour intention are strongly influenced by both cognitive evaluations based on pleasure and arousal cognitive factors. In overall, these results indicate that model of the present study can forecast and clarify the buyer behaviour and responses in terms of store atmospherics based shopping.

7. Implications and Conclusions

This study has practical implication for provided the guidance to increase understanding of atmospherics in clothing stores retailers for better understanding the shopper's behavior in the context of changing buying behavior and psychological response in an emerging factor in retail sector. The finding may help in order to compete, stores need to have a distinctive atmosphere and provide an extraordinary shopping experience both to attract new customers and to retain old customers and also build sustainable competitive advantage is through customer loyalty. Some consumers have less time for shopping, others are not interested in shopping, some enjoy bargain hunting, others like browsing and window shopping and some like to be pampered. No matter how diverse the customers they each encounter a retail experience when shopping.

Concerning the consumer shopping behavior when it comes to buying clothes, it is

changing very fast nowadays, particularly among young people. As more Cloths-related fashioned brands are entering into developing markets. Understanding about atmospheric cues and developing appropriate mix of these factors may help these retailers to generate more revenues. At the same time domestic retailers are facing competition from the global brands therefore this has become critically important for them to understand target customer behaviour and use atmospheric cues smartly and provide ambiance which make positive impact on customers buying behaviour to remain in the competition and further extend their market size. In conclusion retailers need to try to figure out best ways to entertain shoppers and also to make them feel comfortable. They can create a perfect shopping mood by using visual and non-visual cues. It can be said that even though atmospherics is becoming an important concept in retailing, it is still an area to be developed in practice and needs to be further investigated.

References

- Ali, M. S. I., Mubarak, K. M., and Shameem, A., 2017, Interior Atmosphere: Does it Really Have an Impact on Consumer Purchasing Behaviour at Self-Serving Convenience Stores? *Journal of Marketing and Consumer Research*, 31, 28-34.
- Anand, T. and Batra, G. S., 2016, Organized Retailing in Malaysia and India: A Review of Earlier Studies. *Pacific Business Review International*, 8(10), 100-115.
- Areni, C. and Kim, D., 1994, The Influence of In-Store Lighting on Consumers' Examination of Merchandise in a Wine Store. *International Journal of Research in Marketing* 11(2), 117–125.
- Balgaonkar, V., Pabalkar, V. and Yelikar, R., 2014, Visual Merchandising and Purchasing Behaviour of Youth: A Cluster Analysis. *International Journal of Applied Services Marketing Perspectives*, 3(3), 1158-1164.
- Bitner, M. J., 1992, Service scapes: The Impact of Physical Surroundings on Customers and Employees. *Journal of Marketing*, 56, 57-71.
- Borges, A., Babin, B. J. and Spielmann, N., 2013, Gender Orientation and Retail Atmosphere: Effects on Value Perception. *International Journal of Retail and Distribution Management*, 41(7), 498-511.
- Cao, H., 2018, The Growth of E-Commerce and its Impact on the Fast Fashion Retailers. Bachelor's Thesis Degree Programme in International Business, Haaga-Helia University of Applied Sciences, 1-39.
- Chatterjeen, P. and Kumar, A., 2016, Consumer Willingness to Pay across Retail channels. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 34(C), 264-270.

Deloitte, 2016, Navigating the New Digital Divide: A Global Summary of Findings from Nine Countries on Digital Influence in Retail p. 17.

Elena H. and Berčík, J., 2014, The Influence of Light on Consumer Behavior at the Food Market. *Journal of Food Products Marketing*, 20, 429–440.

Farias, S. A., Aguiar, E. C. and Melo, F. V. S., 2014, Store Atmospheric and Experiential Marketing: A Conceptual Framework and Research Propositions for an Extraordinary Customer Experience. *International Business Research*, 7(2), 87-99.

Gandhi, B. M. and Chinnadorai, K. M., 2017, Retail in India. *International Journal of Engineering Development and Research*, 5(1), 433-435.

Hameli, K., 2018, A Literature Review of Retailing Sector and Business Retailing Types. *ILIRIA International Review*, 8(1), 3-24.

Hanaysha, J.R., 2018, An Examination of the Factors Affecting Consumer's Purchase Decision in the Malaysian Retail Market. *PSU Research Review*, 2(1), 7-23.

Hussain, R. and Ali, M., (2015, Effect of Store Atmosphere on Consumer Purchase Intention. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, 7(2), 8-26.

Iannone, R., Ingenito, A., Martino, G., Miranda, S., Pepe, C. and Riemma, S., 2013, Merchandise and Replenishment Planning Optimization for Fashion Retail. *International Journal of Engineering Business Management*, 5(26): 1-14.

Jain, R. and Bagdare, S., 2011, Music and Consumption Experience: A Review. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 39(4), 289-302.

Jang, J. Y., Baek, E., Yoon, S. Y. and Choo, H. J., 2018, Store Design: Visual Complexity and Consumer Responses. *International Journal of Design*, 12(2), 105-118.

Kotler, P., 1973, Atmospheric as a Marketing Tool. *Journal of retailing*, 49(4), 48-64.

KPMG, 2017, The truth About Online Consumers 2017. *Global Online Consumer Report*, 1-36.

Kusuma, B., Prasad, N. D. and Rao, M. S., 2013, A Study on Organized Retailing and its Challenges and Retail Customer Services. *Innovative Journal of Business and Management*, 2(5), 97-102.

Lindberga, U., Salomonson, N., Sundströma, M. and Wendind, K., 2018, Consumer Perception and Behaviour in the Retail Foodscape: Study of Chilled Groceries. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 40, 1–7.

Mathur, M. and Goswami, S., 2014, Store Atmospheric Factors Driving Customer Purchase Intention- An Exploratory Study. *BVIMSR's Journal of Management Research*, 6(2), 111-117.

Mehta, N., 2014, Impact of Visual merchandising on Consumer buying: A study of furniture outlets, *Universal Journal of Management* 2(6), 207-217.

Mihić, M., Anić, I.-D. Milaković, I. K., 2018, Time Spent Shopping and Consumer Clothing Purchasing Behaviour. *Ekonomski Pregled*, 69(2), 89-105.

Milliman, R. E., 1986, The Influence of Background Music on the Behaviour of Restaurant Patrons. *The Journal of Consumer Research*, 13(2), 286-289.

Munshi, A. R., 2018, Impact of Store Atmospherics on Consumer Buying Behaviour at D-Mart Store. *International Journal of Research in Humanities, Arts and Literature*, 6(8), 467-474.

Murray, J., Elms, J. and Teller, C., 2017, Examining the Role of Store Design on Consumers' Cross-Sectional of Retail Brand Loyalty. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 38, 147-156.

Nishanov, B. and Ahunjonov, U., 2016, The influence of Store Characteristics on Consumers' Impulse Buying Behaviour. *Journal of International Business Research and Marketing*, 1(3), 20-26.

Pattanaik, S. and Mishra, B. B., 2016, Evolution of Retail Industry in India. *Journal of Research Innovation and Management Science*, 2(4), 51-55.

Perera, K. J. T. and Sutha, J., 2018, Factors Influence on Consumers' Leisure Shopping Behaviour in Shopping Malls and its Future Research Direction-Literature Review. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 8(2), 203-219.

Priyadarshini, E. and Hamil, A., 2014, Impact of Supermarkets on Unorganized Retail. *International Journal of Research in Business Management*, 2(7), 37-56.

Quartier, K., Vanrie, J. and Van Cleempoel, K., 2014, As Real as it Gets: What Role Does Lighting Have on Consumer's Perception of Atmosphere, Emotions and Behaviour? *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 39, 32-39.

Ridgway, N. M., Dawson, S. A. and Bloch, P., 1989, Pleasure and Arousal in the Marketplace: Interpersonal Differences in Approach-Avoidance Responses. *Marketing Letters* 1(2), 139-147.

Sabrina, E., 2014, The Influence of the Store Atmosphere on the Consumer Behaviour. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(8), 229-235.

Santos, E. B. A. and Freire, O. B. L., 2013, The Influence of Music on Consumer Purchase Behavior in Retail Environment. *Independent Journal of Management and Production*, 4(2), 537-548.

Shamsher, R., 2015, Store Image and its Impact on Consumer Behaviour. *Elk Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Retail Management*, 7(2), 1-27.

Thahir, A. and Krishnapillai, G., 2017, How Does the Ambience of Cafe Affect the Revisit Intention Among its Patrons? As on the Cafes in Ipoh, Perak. *MATEC Web of Conferences*, 150, 1-16.